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A Qualitative Study on MBHTE-BARMM Supervisors’ Approaches to Achieving Work-Life Responsibilities

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Abstract

This study explores the approaches employed by supervisors in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) in attaining work-life responsibilities. Employing a qualitative study design, it delves into the experiences of the research participants in their strive to balance their professional roles with personal life commitments. Data collection involved in-depth interviews, observation, and narrative analysis, involving a sample of twenty-five (25) supervisors from diverse divisions and programs in the BARMM. The findings of the study unveil several crucial dimensions of the participants’ experiences and strategies. It becomes apparent that they experienced multitasking hence, learned to prioritize tasks which is a testament to the dynamic and multifaceted nature of their roles. In terms of strategies, the study reveals that they predominantly rely on time management and advance planning to deal with the balancing of work and personal life. Moreover, personal, and professional factors that affect their approach to achieving work-life balance include personal problems, inability to balance time, and commitment to work. The research participants also face specific challenges such as resource shortages and overwhelming workloads. This study further highlights the participants’ expected support from schools and districts through communication and mutual understanding. Based on the findings of the study, a model was generated. This model reveals three dimensions of work-life responsibilities namely (1) personal and professional responsibilities, (2) internal support, and (3) external support.

Keywords: Work-Life Responsibilities, Phenomenological Study, Education Supervisors, Work-Life Balance

1. Introduction

In today’s fast-paced and demanding world, finding a balance between work and life has become increasingly challenging. As people strive to excel in their careers, meet deadlines, and achieve professional success, it is easy to lose sight of the importance of personal well-being and quality time with loved ones. Balancing work and life are not just about managing time effectively; it is about prioritizing one’s physical and mental health, nurturing relationships, and finding fulfillment in both professional and personal spheres.

Balancing work-life among career employees or career-oriented individuals, for instance, school administrators, is more challenging. Among authors on stress and mindfulness, Oishi and Westgate (2022) asserted that living an

authentic life with a sense of purpose and balance is the key to true happiness. This sentiment emphasizes the importance of maintaining a work-life balance, as work and personal life are interconnected. Similarly, Mayaer (2022) described work-life as the effective management of professional and personal demands. As such, it is crucial for school administrators like supervisors, to prioritize work-life balance to maintain their wellbeing, promote a healthy work environment, increase productivity and performance, and experience higher career satisfaction.

According to Leshner (2012), supervisors serve as educational leaders who work in divisions and departments across the academy. Wilk (2013) added that supervisors are present in the superintendent's office, student affairs, athletics, development, academic departments, and other areas. While faculty have academic and instructional responsibilities, administrators are responsible for addressing students' non-instructional needs, engaging in day-to-day problem solving, and facilitating long-term institutional planning.

In fact, they are expected to undertake administrative work and often work long hours, face a heavy workload that may negatively impact their personal relationships due to lack of energy, time, and commitment. Because of this, supervisors struggle to balance personal and professional concerns, leading to positive and negative spillover (Bell, et al., 2012). When conflict between work and family occurs, it can have adverse effects not only on organizations but also on employees and their families. Similarly, Whitehead and Kotze (2003) as cited in Baltes, et al. (2011) argued that work-family conflict has negative impact on both organizational and individual-level outcomes hence, work-life balance is a crucial aspect of a supervisors' lives, particularly in the context of their professional careers.

Previous studies on work-life balance shed light on different factors influencing work-life balance, such as sociocultural challenges (Edwards & Oten, 2019), parenting (Dapiton et al., 2020), single-parenting (Alonge & Osagiobare, 2020; Encila & Madrigal, 2021), resilience during a pandemic (McBrayer et al., 2022), remote teaching (Rawal, 2023; Dulay, 2022), gender (Persson & Hakansson, 2018), demographic variables, administrative staff burnout, among others. By examining these studies, it provides comprehensive understanding on the complexities surrounding work-life balance and the implications for various professional roles and gaps in literature.

Edwards and Oten (2019) highlighted the sociocultural challenges faced by female teachers when balancing domestic roles and teaching. Their study revealed the importance of considering cultural factors in addressing work-life balance. In the study by Denson and Szelényi's (2022), it showed that single faculty members had a lower work-life balance compared to married/partnered faculty. Aside from civil status, gender is also a crucial factor. In the study of Persson and Hakansson (2018), they identified gender-related stressors among Filipinos – women experience more stress due to balancing multiple responsibilities, while men felt greater pressure to provide for their families.

Moreover, Dapiton et al. (2020) focused on the role of parenting in moderating work-life balance, particularly among female academics in the Philippines. The study highlighted the need for support systems to help balance family commitments and research productivity. Alonge and Osagiobare (2020) and Encila and Madrigal (2021) also conducted a study on parenthood and work-life balance in Nigeria and the Philippines, respectively participated by single-parents or solo-parents. The latter's paper revealed that solo-parent administrators used coping mechanisms and time management to balance their roles effectively while the former's study found that single-parent teachers face challenges in job productivity, but there was no significant relationship between work-life balance and job productivity.

In some studies, the context of work-life balance was investigated during the time of COVID19 pandemic or the challenges of remote teaching. McBrayer et al. (2020) conducted a study on school leadership during a global health pandemic which revealed that teachers are committed to their careers despite the challenges of teaching during a crisis. Protective factors, such as energy levels and meaningful connections, play a role in preventing teacher burnout. Rawal (2023) also found that teachers, specifically female teachers, experienced stress due to long hours of work during pandemic. Meanwhile, the study of Dulay (2022) revealed the various challenges teachers faced during emergency remote teaching, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Such challenges

included workspace inadequacy and irregular working hours, which affected both work and personal life. Moreover, Kandemir and Nartgün's (2022) study found that distance education negatively affected teachers' work-life balance, leading to role conflict and interference with family duties.

Furthermore, burnout at work was also found to be one factor influencing work-life balance. Li and Ye (2022) investigated burnout among administrative staff in a university setting and identified a significant relationship between role conflict, ambiguity, and burnout. This highlighted the importance of addressing workload and role clarity among administrative staff. This study confirmed the findings of Rath (2020) who explored administrators' experiences during restructuring, emphasizing the significance of building relationships and coping with emotions during transitions. Lastly, Raabe (2021) also reported problems managing the conflicting demands of work and their life.

These aforementioned studies on work-life balance appear to be focused among teachers and parents while only a few studies explored work-life balance among supervisors or administrators. In fact, few studies have been conducted to investigate the approaches and strategies dealing with supervisors' work-life responsibilities, more specifically those from the BARMM. The voices and struggles of the supervisors in balancing their career and personal lives made it imperative and interesting to explore this area of research. Thus, to fill in the gap and issues with the work-life balance among supervisors, this study described the experiences of selected supervisors in BARMM to describe and explore their approaches, strategies, and challenges in attaining balanced work-life responsibilities. Furthermore, it aims to contribute to the body of knowledge in educational leadership, particularly on the topic of work and life responsibilities by proposing a model of work-life responsibilities among supervisors.

2. Method

This study employed qualitative approach to explore the work-life responsibilities of supervisors. This is an appropriate design because it provides valuable insights into the unique and subjective aspects of the experiences of the research participants. According to Giorgi (2012), this focuses on exploring the experiences of individuals. It aims to cover the essences of experiences and the way people make meaning of them. Hence, this methodology allows researchers to explore how supervisors perceive and make sense of their work and personal lives, the challenges they face, the approaches they use, and the strategies they employ to balance these aspects. Their experiences were examined through interview sessions, observation of their typical day at work, and their personal narrative reports.

This study was conducted within Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM) in the Philippines. The researchers deemed that this would be the ideal research setting as the need was felt to conduct this study in MBHTE (Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education) in BARMM to improve the approaches of BARMM supervisors in achieving work-life responsibilities. In addition, given the different cultures that comprise the Bangsamoro people, it would be interesting to see different experiences and different perspectives, as well as different strategies for work-life balance based on the responses of the participants on their individual contexts.

To identify the participants, purposive sampling was done. It was an appropriate sampling method in this study for the very reason that it allowed the researchers to target a specific group of interest that aligns with the research question (Baumgartner and Schneider, 2010). The research participants of the study were twenty-five (25) supervisors from different division areas and programs in BARMM who met the criteria and were willing to participate. They were chosen as participants because of their status, experience, and knowledge in their respective fields. The selection criteria for the participants were mother, married, have children, with a minimum of two (2) years of experience as supervisors, prior to becoming supervisors, and teachers. There were four (4) participants in each division while five (5) participants in Marawi City who met the given criteria. The career experiences of all the participants clearly demonstrated that they are devoted to their work and passionate about education. The information described their individual demographic characteristics both personally and professionally, their educational experience and their current family status.

Thematic analysis was utilized in the study. The following were the steps utilized by the researchers to analyze the collected data: First, the interview recordings were transcribed. Prior to transcribing, the technique of bracketing was applied by the researchers. Bracketing is a technique used to suspend or set aside the researcher's knowledge, perceptions, or attitudes towards the phenomenon (Creswell, 2014). After the bracketing method, the interview data were then transcribed. Second, the interview transcripts were read several times by the researchers for more familiarity and understanding of the essence of the experiences of the participants. Coding was then followed. After coding, the keywords were categorized to generate themes. Thematic analysis is a common tool in qualitative research which is a useful and accessible tool that enables researchers to generate new insights and concepts derived from the data. The last stage of the data analysis was the generation of a model. The model was generated after a critical analysis of the themes that emerged from the data. The researchers came up with dimensions that would describe a model of work-life responsibilities that frame the experiences of supervisors in BARMM.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Experiences of Supervisors in Achieving Work-Life Responsibilities

3.1.1. Multi-tasking

Supervisors play various roles and responsibilities, especially in the Department of Education. Thus, multi-tasking was one of the common experiences that the participants shared. Having excellent multitasking skills may even allow an employee to maintain his/her position in the organization. In many ways, multitasking appears like a good habit by working on more than one task at once and multitaskers are proven to be more productive. However, even though multitaskers might seem better at their work, several studies reveal that multitasking harms productivity.

Based on this study, eight (8) out of twenty-five (25) participants answered multi-tasking as one of their experiences. According to the participants, as they shared the various responsibilities playing their role as supervisors, multi-tasking has become an important tool in their workplace. With intense pressure on time and finishing multiple tasks, not to mention their responsibilities at home, they were forced to multi-task to save time. This also came with managing their own time.

This finding reveals that supervisors play various roles and responsibilities. The scope of work of a supervisor that he or she needs to supervise is relatively wide based on district or educational programs. Supervisors in the MBHTE – BARMM engaged in a wide array of tasks, including overseeing educational programs, managing personnel, ensuring compliance with educational policies, and addressing the diverse needs of students and educators. This multifaceted responsibility indicated the depth and breadth of their involvement in the education system.

This study aligns with previous research highlighting work overload and multitasking as challenges. Li and Ye (2022) found administrative staff experiencing burnout due to workload, confirming similar feelings among participants in this study. While multitasking is often seen as a positive skill, research by Dux (2014) and Gafman (2013) shows it negatively impacts individual and organizational productivity. This includes reduced quality, workflow inconsistencies, and lack of preparation. These findings suggest potential areas for addressing workload and promoting focused work within the organization.

3.1.2. Making Priorities

The participants had first shared that one of their experiences was to multi-task due to their heavy workload. Following this was their experience of prioritizing to balance their work and their life at home with their family. Thus, as they are bombarded with countless tasks and demands, the theme of the importance of making priorities emerged from the participants' inputs. Based on the data of the study, five (5) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that making priorities was one of their experiences. Due to hectic schedules and responsibilities, participants

shared that they had to make priorities sometimes that either compromise their work and their families or successfully achieve a balanced work-life responsibilities.

These findings depicted a complex relationship between the prioritization of work over personal life, the establishment of boundaries and schedules, the delegation of tasks, and the acknowledgment of the need for balance between various roles in the case of supervisors in MBHTE – BARMM. These also suggested that supervisors employed various strategies to manage their work-life responsibilities, with some expressing the challenges of sacrificing personal time for professional duties, while others emphasized the importance of proactive planning and support systems.

This study aligns with research emphasizing the importance of prioritization for work-life balance. Yang (2020) and Marsh-Girardi (2011) advocate for prioritizing tasks, especially for supervisors, to manage time effectively. However, Asfahani (2021) highlights the potential of prioritization to create conflict and distress when focusing on one aspect over the other. This underscores the need for a nuanced approach to prioritization that considers individual contexts and the potential for negative consequences.

3.2. Strategies Supervisors Used to Achieve Work-Life Responsibilities

3.2.1. Time Management with Priorities

Given the complex roles of supervisors, the participants shared that their main strategy to achieve work-life responsibilities was to have the time management, with emphasis on prioritization. Based on the data, eight (8) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that time management was one of their strategies. The reflective decision making shared by the participants was a thoughtful approach beneficial to time management.

These findings implied that the research participants applied a proactive approach to managing time and ensuring that there were no overlapping commitments. This proactive approach could contribute to reducing stress and allowing supervisors to better balance their professional and personal commitments. Micro-strategies such as collaboration and effective communication with colleagues could play a crucial role in managing work responsibilities, especially when an individual could not handle everything independently. Moreover, with the kind of culture and tradition that Moro people are known for, such as having strong ties with kinship entails that in every event or ceremony, it is part of their social obligations to attend or be present in it hence adding to the avalanche of work-responsibilities in their personal and professional lives. Nonetheless, it can be said that time management and prioritization help them in managing their complex responsibilities as supervisors.

Participants' micro-strategies like scheduling, planning, and organizing align with existing research on effective time management (TM) for work-life balance (WLB). This supports Sahito et al.'s (2016) claim that efficient TM involves planning, organizing, and implementing tasks to achieve goals and ensure employee and organizational sustainability. While TM lacks a universal definition, Eilam and Aharon (2003) emphasize its importance in monitoring and controlling time for task completion. Studies like Encila and Madrigal (2021) and Grissom et al. (2015) demonstrate the effectiveness of TM in balancing roles and reducing job stress. Additionally, Khodaveis et al. (2015) and Macan (1994) link improved TM skills to reduced stress and physical symptoms, highlighting its positive impact on quality of life.

3.2.2. Advance Planning

Planning for the preparation and support for current schools and districts' programs, activities, and others is important to supervisors and for educational leadership programs. Based on the data gathered, five (5) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that advance planning is an important strategy. Time management coupled with advance planning for all the tasks that needed to be done both at work and home is of critical importance to supervisors and institutions of higher learning that have educational leadership programs. As gleaned from the interview transcripts, it highlighted the importance of time management and planning as another essential strategies for achieving work-life balance among supervisors.

Educational leaders, like supervisors, are charged with guiding teachers and others to improve the learning experience for all students, K-12 and beyond, while also respecting their cultural differences. Studies have shown that ineffective planning causes poor teaching and hazy preparation of a budget. Inadequate funds to procure materials needed for planning and supervisors' not involving the concerned staff in planning are also causes of poor planning. Government should provide periodic in-service training on planning for principals and principals should practice good communication skills (Manafa, 2019). Supervisors must establish laborious yet attainable planning to assess the loads of work that they need to do and the process of planning and time management on the part of the supervisors helped improve the schools' or education's need for effective planning, implementing and monitoring and evaluation of various programs of the division. This is a way of determining the gaps between the current school condition and the potential for improvement. To the highest level of effectiveness, the school planning must be in dynamic procedures to engage data and people.

3.2.3. Self-Care and Health

Taking care of one's physical and mental health is crucial for a supervisor to maintain productivity and well-being as they navigate through their complex array of responsibilities. Eight (8) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that self-care and health were other noted strategies. In terms of self-care and good health, participants shared specific ways to maintain this aspect such as recognizing body as capital maintenance, having good physical, spiritual and mental health, and being aware of aging and the consequences that come with it hence taking medication to keep a healthy body.

These findings on self-care and health as one of the strategies employed by the participants to achieve work-life responsibilities illustrated a multi-faceted and proactive approach to self-care and health among supervisors in MBHTE - BARMM. The emphasis on exercise as a form of self-care aligned with the understanding that physical activity has numerous health benefits, including stress reduction and increased energy levels. The importance of providing necessary vitamins for the body indicated an awareness of nutritional needs.

This perhaps may be understandable given that BARMM is a region mostly inhabited by Muslims who firmly believe that one's health and body must be prioritized and taken care of. This is inspired from the hadith or saying of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) that a person's body has a right over him or her; suggesting for every Muslim to take care of his or her health as it is part of one's duty to protect and take care of his or her body. In addition, this also implied a holistic approach to health, considering both macro-level factors such as sleep and micronutrients. Thus, self-care and health are recognized as crucial strategies employed by supervisors to achieve work-life balance and responsibilities.

Recent studies also underscored the essence of health and well-being. Mayaer (2022) described work-life as the effective management of professional and personal demands that include prioritizing work-life balance to maintain their wellbeing, promote a healthy work environment, increase productivity and performance, and experience higher career satisfaction. McBrayer et al. (2020) shared that the protective factors, such as energy levels and meaningful connections, play a role in preventing burnout. Lastly, Hinds (2022) emphasized that supervisors, who juggle from one work to another, need to make the work manageable and to have healthy balance between personal and professional responsibilities. Acknowledging the various strategies of self-care and health, it is a good indication that the supervisors from BARMM are employing this strategy which help them become more effective and efficient as they try to keep the equilibrium between their work and domestic roles.

3.2.4. Open Communication

Having the ability to express the individual's thoughts while interacting with other people is an open communication. It is an ability to provide ideas, information, and suggestions, to give and receive feedback, and raise concerns to make the participants active in the workplace. Nine (9) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared similar strategy and stressed the significance of having open communication, especially with their colleagues.

These findings entailed that in the context of MBHTE – BARMM, clear and effective open communication among supervisors were seen as a fundamental strategy to accomplishing work-life responsibilities. Open lines of communication could lead to better coordination and understanding among team members. This strategy suggested that a supportive and inclusive communication style contributed to positive relations and, in turn, enhances work-life balance. The focus on disseminating correct information implied that accurate and timely communication was essential for successful task execution among the research participants. Moreover, the use of technology and other channels to communicate showed that supervisors aimed to properly communicate with their subordinates and enhance overall efficiency.

Selzer et al. (2017) enumerated various characteristics of a leader namely the ability to know the communication styles, and ability to promote cooperation, collaboration, and communication style. Robertson (2016) also claimed that administrators should emphasize teamwork and authentic communication as a key to success. Likewise, according to Rao and Mohan (2008), achieving a certain level of personal growth could be related to the quality of communication in the organization and more to the rewarding nature of the job where employees preferred adequate challenges without compromising their work values. Henceforth, effective communication, collaboration within teams, and the utilization of modern communication tools were essential strategies for supervisors to achieve their work-life responsibilities. These strategies contributed to a supportive work environment, facilitate the sharing of information, and enhanced overall efficiency in managing both professional and personal aspects of life of the research participants.

3.2.5. Spiritual Guidance through Prayers

Reflecting on individual's life direction and growing by recognizing the presence of God is the notion of spiritual guidance. Seven (7) out of twenty-five (25) participants considered seeking spiritual guidance or praying to Allah (God) as another common strategy employed by the participants. The primary strategy discussed in the data was the religious aspect of praying and asking guidance from a higher power, particularly from Allah.

These findings implied that supervisors in the BARMM were practicing Muslims who were aware of their duties as Muslims and had strong beliefs in the guidance of Allah (God) and His plan. It suggested that maintaining a positive mindset through prayers was an essential aspect of dealing with the myriads of roles and responsibilities of a supervisor in the MBHTE - BARMM. The participants advocated trusting in a higher power to guide them in both professional and personal aspects of life. This trust was seen as a source of comfort and assurance in facing the demands of their supervisory roles. Furthermore, the participants employed a unique blend of spiritual and practical strategies to cope with the demands of their supervisory roles. Simultaneously, there was an acknowledgment of the need for self-care, positive thinking, and breaks from work-related stress.

This study delves into a novel aspect of work-life balance (WLB) by exploring the role of spiritual guidance among Muslim supervisors in BARMM. Existing research on WLB lacks such focus. Interestingly, participants identified prayer as a coping mechanism, highlighting the influence of their strong spiritual beliefs on managing work-life challenges. This finding aligns with studies on WLB and Islamic perspectives, demonstrating a positive link between religiosity and WLB. For example, Yusuf and Sajid Khan (2015) found a positive relationship between WLB and well-being among religious employees compared to their non-religious counterparts. These findings suggest that, for these supervisors, spirituality and self-care are interconnected strategies for achieving WLB. This unique combination offers a potentially valuable framework for managing supervisory challenges while maintaining overall well-being. Further research can explore the specific practices and mechanisms through which spirituality contributes to WLB in this context.

3.3. Factors Affecting Supervisors' Approaches to Achieving Work-Life Responsibilities

3.3.1. Personal Life and Family

Eight (8) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that one of the common factors that affected the participants' approaches to achieving work-life responsibilities was their ability to deal properly with matters of their personal

and family life. These findings implied that external demands, such as social obligations or domestic responsibilities with their spouses and children, could impact a supervisor's ability to manage his or her work-life balance, as in the case in BARMM. The BARMM region, which is predominantly inhabited by Muslims, for example the Meranaws, emphasized the value on family and social obligations. The Meranaw people are known for attaching great importance to their familial and social responsibilities.

These cultural and social norms may have implications to the work-life balance of supervisors in the MBHTE - BARMM. It suggested that external demands, such as fulfilling social obligations or attending to domestic responsibilities could have an impact on a supervisor's ability to effectively manage their work-life responsibilities in this specific cultural and regional context. The finding further suggested that these external demands from their personal lives may affect how well supervisors could juggle their work responsibilities with their family and social commitments, potentially making it challenging for them to maintain a satisfactory work-life balance.

This study aligns with previous research highlighting the impact of family on work-life balance (WLB) for supervisors. Studies by Li and Ye (2022) and Bell et al. (2012) demonstrate the "spillover" effect, where work-family conflict negatively impacts individuals, families, and organizations. This conflict reduces job satisfaction and affects WLB, as shown by Talukder (2019).

However, research findings are mixed. While Whitehead and Kotze (2003) found no individual-level impact, supervisors in this study identified family-related challenges as hindering their WLB achievement. Supporting this, Dapiton et al. (2020) recommend support systems to manage family commitments and work productivity.

3.3.2. Inability to Balance time

It can be quite challenging if time, which is the most limited and most precious resource available to the administrators, is not well managed. Five (5) out of twenty-five (25) participants mentioned lack of time as the main factor in failing to do what school heads needed to accomplish. Some participants manifested about what they wanted to do but could not accomplish while others mentioned having to take shortcuts that were not adequate solutions.

The results underscored the issue of time constraints in the lives of supervisors. These supervisors were aware of the need for rest and relaxation, struggle with prioritization due to limited time, and acknowledge the impact of time constraints on both personal and professional aspects of their lives.

This study aligns with researches highlighting the time pressures faced by supervisors like the participants. As noted by Britton and Glynn (2013), juggling high demands in limited time is common for intellectually productive professionals. For supervisors, this translates to managing school operations, programs, and staff relations – all time-intensive tasks.

Effective time management emerges as a crucial strategy for increasing productivity and well-being in this context. Similar to previous WLB studies (Grissom et al., 2015; Soomro et al., 2018; Mendis & Weerakkody, 2017), this study finds a clear connection between strong time management skills and reduced stress, improved job satisfaction, and ultimately, better job performance. This aligns with Kamran et al. (2014) suggesting flexible work arrangements like reduced hours can positively impact both WLB and productivity. These findings suggest exploring time management techniques and flexible work policies as potential avenues to support supervisors, enhance their well-being, and consequently improve school outcomes.

3.3.3. Commitment to Work

Achieving a harmonious balance between personal and professional responsibilities is a perennial challenge for education supervisors. From the various struggles of juggling from one task to another, driven by their commitments to their personal and professional qualities, the participants shed light on various dimensions that impacted their work-life responsibilities. Seven (7) out of 25 participants answered commitment to work as another factor affecting supervisors' approaches to work-life responsibilities.

Understanding the multifaceted nature of factors influencing the ways supervisors approached their work-life responsibilities held significant implications in the context of BARMM. This means that school's division in MBHTE - BARMM may benefit from promoting environments that align with individuals' sense of purpose, emphasizing the integration of personal and professional qualities. Recognizing and supporting the diverse challenges among BARMM supervisors related to commitments, childcare, and health could contribute to more holistic well-being of supervisors. Lastly, promoting a work-life culture that values devotion, passion, and commitment may enhance job satisfaction and productivity, ultimately leading and promoting a healthier work-life responsibilities for supervisors.

Dapiton et al. (2020) highlighted the need for support systems to help balance family commitments and research productivity. In another study, commitment appeared to have high impact on WLB like the study of Hausman et al. (2002) that revealed that in terms of work-life indicators such as professional commitment, community support, sense of efficacy, goal congruence, and balance between personal and professional life; the only indicator with a low rating was balance. This meant that the participants struggled with commitments, thus, having difficulty in balancing their personal and professional lives.

3.4. Challenges Encountered by Supervisors in Achieving Work-Life Responsibilities

3.4.1. Lack of Resources

Achieving work-life responsibilities is a constant struggle for many professionals, particularly supervisors who shoulder the responsibility of managing both the demands of their work and personal lives. Ten (10) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared that one of the major challenges they encountered was lack of resources.

The findings entailed the urgent need for the BARMM to address the various challenges faced by supervisors in achieving work-life responsibilities, specifically on lack of resources. Recognizing the limitations imposed by inadequate time, budget constraints, and technological gaps, lack of resources was crucial in creating supportive measures. The MBHTE-BARMM must consider implementing strategies to streamline processes, allocate sufficient resources, and provide the necessary support structures. Furthermore, the study highlighted the need for contextual solutions, particularly in regions undergoing transitions like BARMM. Policymakers and leaders should work towards finalizing and implementing key frameworks, such as education codes, to ensure that supervisors have the necessary tools and budgets aligned with their responsibilities. Failure to address these challenges not only impacts the well-being of supervisors but also hampers the overall effectiveness of programs and initiatives.

According to Owoko (2010), the term resources referred not only to teaching methods and materials but also the time available for instruction, the knowledge and skills of teachers acquired through training and experience. Teaching pupils with special needs in the inclusive classroom deviated from the regular programme. Pupils with special needs may require more instruction time, other learning methods and professional knowledge. This could be achieved by an increase in resources or by re-arranging available resources. Children with special needs are not required to meet the classroom standards, rather the classroom meets the individual needs of all children (Bargma, 2000). Puri and Abraham (2004) argued that school management and teachers should make efforts to identify and attend to learners with special learning needs for instance dietary needs especially pre-school. Oyugi and Nyaga (2010) noted that teaching and learning resources include peripatetic services, support staff (sign language interpreters and Braille transcribers), community involvement, regular and special teachers among others.

Inadequately trained special education teachers and professionals acts as an obstacle to implementation of inclusive education (Kochung, 2011).

3.4.2. Overlapping Workloads

Overlapping workloads happen when the end of one activity, program, etc. overlaps with the start of another. Through the interviews with twelve (12) out of twenty-five (25) participants, it was evident that the demands of their roles significantly impact their personal lives, leading to sacrifices and struggles in managing time effectively due to their overlapping workloads.

These findings implied the need for officials in the MBHTE – BARMM to balance work commitments that needed meticulous planning to prevent overlaps and to ensure efficient time management among supervisors. The findings also underscored the complex challenges that supervisors faced in trying to resolve their work and personal life. The sacrifices made, time constraints, and the impact on personal well-being highlighted the need for organizational support and flexibility. This support may begin at the top level in the MBHTE – BARMM.

This study aligns with prior research highlighting workload challenges faced by both new and experienced school leaders. Sarwar et al. (2012) and Oleszewski et al. (2012) emphasize the burden of administrative tasks on teachers and supervisors, impacting their teaching and leadership effectiveness. Studies by Wambui et al. (2017) and Sirgy and Lee (2017) further illustrate diverse challenges like resource limitations, accountability demands, and student discipline.

3.5. *Schools and Districts' Support for Supervisors in Achieving Work-Life Responsibilities*

3.5.1. Proper Communication

For communication to be effective, communication skills needed to be appropriately observed such as learning to interact with others, and discuss issues, concerns, and problems. Twelve (12) out of twenty-five (25) participants shared proper communication as one of the supports that the participants received from schools and districts.

The findings underscored the critical role of effective communication and strategic dialogue in fostering a supportive environment for supervisors. The emphasis on transparent communication with higher-ups, particularly superintendents, suggested that the culture or norms in an organization played an important role in facilitating work-life balance. Schools and districts may consider formalizing and strengthening communication channels, fostering an atmosphere where supervisors felt comfortable expressing their needs and challenges. Training programs that enhanced communication skills and promote understanding between supervisors and higher-ups could also contribute to a healthier work environment.

On the other hand, in BARMM where there are diverse ethno-linguistic groups, effective communication among supervisors requires a nuanced approach. The term "ethno-linguistic groups" refers to communities that share not only a common language but also cultural and ethnic ties. The first aspect mentioned is the language used for communication. The diversity of ethno-linguistic groups in BARMM implies that there may be various languages spoken among supervisors. To facilitate effective open communication, BARMM supervisors need to be proficient in the languages relevant to their teams or colleagues. This linguistic diversity poses a need for language-sensitive communication strategies, ensuring that information is accurately conveyed and understood across different language backgrounds.

Aligning with Mohammadi (2010), the study emphasizes the need to go beyond mere language fluency and be attuned to sociolinguistic nuances like non-verbal cues and formality levels. This ensures that communication is not only accurate but also respectful and fosters strong working relationships. Further, drawing on Sryono (2017) and Smith et al. (2017), the study underscores the critical role of effective communication in achieving educational goals. Recognizing and adapting to diverse communication styles within BARMM schools becomes crucial for supervisors to effectively lead, inform, and collaborate with stakeholders. This cultural sensitivity not only

enhances individual well-being but also contributes to the overall effectiveness and sustainability of educational leadership in the region.

3.5.2. Cooperation and Active Participation

Through the interview with seven (7) out of twenty-five (25) participants, they considered cooperation and active participation as another support that may come from schools and districts that would help the supervisors in achieving their work-life responsibilities. This common perspective among supervisors on the support they need from schools and districts in facilitating their work-life responsibilities shed light on the complex ways in which schools and districts could extend assistance. The participants disclosed various forms of support to which the schools and districts could provide active participation and cooperation. This encompassed financial support, administrative support, cooperative efforts, involvement, coaching, and constructive feedback.

The identified support mechanisms through cooperation and active participation of schools and districts implied that fostering a conducive environment for BARMM supervisors involved a comprehensive approach. Schools and districts in the MBHTE - BARMM may consider aligning their budgetary allocations with the diverse needs of projects, streamlining administrative processes, and emphasizing cooperative efforts among their teachers and other stakeholders. Additionally, recognizing the importance of competent and committed leadership at the school and district levels suggested that investing in professional development and leadership training could enhance the overall effectiveness of educational supervision. Ultimately, these insights could guide MBHTE - BARMM in formulating policies and practices that prioritize the well-being and success of educational supervisors, contributing to a more robust and sustainable educational system.

This study aligns with prior research on support systems' effectiveness. While Edwards and Oten (2019) found mixed results regarding their impact on teacher resilience, Dapiton et al. (2020) highlight the need for support, particularly for female academics, in balancing family and work. Interestingly, supervisors in this study identified "cooperation and active participation from school heads" as a key support need. This resonates with Selzer et al.'s (2017) view of leaders fostering cooperation and Yang's (2020) emphasis on collaboration to share workload and achieve better work-life balance (WLB). These findings suggest that providing supervisors with collaborative support structures, alongside addressing identified needs like school head engagement, could potentially enhance their WLB and overall well-being.

3.5.3. Proposed Model of Work-Life Responsibilities

The findings of the study based on the various aspects of work-life responsibilities among supervisors revealed the tough job that a supervisor must face. Nonetheless, despite these challenges and predicaments, they were able to pull through and balance the various hats they were wearing. Building from the themes generated, Figure 1 below displays the proposed model of work-life responsibilities.

Figure 1: Model of Work-Life Responsibilities

As shown in Figure 1, the proposed model of work-life responsibilities has three components: personal and professional aspects, the internal support, and the external support. The model emphasized the hierarchy, and the organization of constructs and factors that should be taken into consideration when a supervisor attempts to balance his or her work-life responsibilities. At the bottom of the diagram was the personal and professional responsibilities which emphasized the determination of the two core duties and responsibilities of a supervisor in the basic education. This underscored the need for supervisors to be aware that their job as supervisors is expected to be complex and critical because of the two responsibilities expected of them to fulfill.

Following this, the second dimension was internal support. This highlighted the intrinsic aspects or abilities and skills that supervisors needed in order to manage well and create that balance between their personal and professional duties. These abilities appeared to be requisites that would help the supervisors to somehow balance their work-life responsibilities.

Lastly, the last dimension was the external support. External support was another crucial factor that kept the balance in the work-life responsibilities of supervisors. These external supports that come from people scaffolded the achievement of work-life balance that may bring sanity, peace, and general well-being among supervisors.

In a nutshell, the model provided a structured approach for supervisors to navigate their work-life responsibilities, emphasizing the interplay between personal and professional aspects, internal support, and external support. Understanding and addressing these dimensions were essential for supervisors not only in the BARMM region but in other regions aiming to achieve a harmonious balance in their professional and personal lives, too.

4. Conclusion

This study delved into the approaches used by supervisors in the BARMM region to achieve work-life balance. The findings shed light on several key aspects of their experiences and strategies. First, it was evident that supervisors in this region frequently engaged in multitasking and prioritized tasks to manage their roles effectively. This underscored the dynamic and multifaceted nature of their responsibilities.

In terms of strategies, the study revealed that time management and advance planning were fundamental tools employed by the study participants to manage the challenges of balancing work and personal life. These strategies enabled them to allocate their resources properly and maintain control over their demanding roles. However, some factors significantly affected their ability to attain work-life responsibilities such as dealing with family problems, struggles with time management, and the strong commitment to work. Furthermore, supervisors faced distinct challenges in their pursuit of balanced work-life responsibilities, including a lack of resources and overlapping excessive workloads. These challenges placed an additional burden on their already demanding roles. Lastly, the study highlighted that effective support from schools and districts revolved around communication and cooperation and active participation. This emphasized the importance of fostering open and empathetic forms of communication between supervisors and their educational institutions to better address their unique needs.

In conclusion, the study proposed a three-dimensional model of supervisor's work-life responsibilities, highlighting the interconnected nature of external support from family, colleagues, and superiors, the need for internal psychological and emotional support, and the myriad personal and professional responsibilities that supervisors must navigate. This model provided a holistic framework for understanding and addressing the complex interplay of factors influencing supervisors' work-life dynamics.

The findings confirm or corroborate much of the research done previously on the same lines. School administrators such as supervisors, especially those who are partnered and with families, undergo and encounter a great deal of stress and strain which affect their work-life balance, but with continued support from within and outside of the family, some time management, some prioritizing and planning, these are all manageable and thus, supervisors are able to have that equilibrium between work and life. In addition, the data and its accompanying analysis has been able to give a reasonable, if not profound, understanding of the theories used in the study.

In light of the aforementioned findings of the study, the implications drawn from this study were far-reaching and these deserve to be translated into actions by the BARMM in particular and in the country in general. The MBHTE and educational institutions in the BARMM may consider policies institutionalizing and incorporating the identified strategies into training programs (such as seminars, or workshops) for their supervisors, emphasizing the importance of time management, self-care, and open communication. Furthermore, the structural challenges highlighted to underscore the need for resource allocation and workload management reforms at the institutional level to facilitate a more conducive work environment. Furthermore, the call for support from schools and districts implied the necessity of fostering a collaborative culture, where financial, administrative, and emotional assistance are integral components. Implementing supportive policies and practices, along with enhancing communication and cooperation among stakeholders, could significantly contribute to a more sustainable and balanced work-life for supervisors. Finally, the proposed three-dimensional model provided a comprehensive framework for guiding future research and intervention efforts, ensuring a better understanding of the intricate challenges and support structures that supervisors navigated in their professional journeys. Thus, the better the supervisors are in terms of work-life balance, the better their performance will be and possibly their job satisfaction levels will increase. There is much for the BARMM and the MBHTE to do along this line, but the results of this study and that of other researchers all point out that the above-mentioned conclusions will be beneficial not only to the target persons concerned, but also for the school constituents and the community as well.

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